

Oral Presentation #83 was presented at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is part of the proceedings titled: Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress.

AUTHORS

Elif Negis

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4070-3558>

Yasemin Kilic Ozturk

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1463-6627>

AFFILIATIONS

Izmir Kiraz No. 1 Family Health Center
Izmir, Turkey

University of Health Sciences
Tepecik Training and Research Hospital
Department of Family Medicine
Izmir, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: This study evaluates the relationship between media coverage and public awareness of HIV/AIDS using Google Trends data. Despite significant advancements in HIV care, HIV/AIDS continues to be a critical public health concern globally.

Materials and Methods: Using Google Trends data from January 2004 to January 2025, this study examined the impact of media reports on public interest in HIV in Turkey, focusing on specific spikes in search interest during key events in 2018 and 2024.

Results: The results revealed significant increases in search interest following media coverage of events such as a controversy involving a hospital's refusal to treat an HIV-positive patient in 2018, and a rise in HIV cases among university students in 2024. Regional variations in search interest mirrored the geographic areas where these events were reported.

Conclusion: This study highlights the effectiveness of media in driving public awareness and the potential of online tools like Google Trends to monitor shifts in public interest in health-related issues. These findings underscore the importance of using media proactively to increase health literacy and raise awareness of infectious diseases, with implications for public health policy and communication strategies.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

HIV/AIDS, public awareness, media influence, google trends, infodemiology

INTRODUCTION

Despite extensive efforts to combat the disease over many years, HIV/AIDS remains a major global public health issue (UNAIDS, 2020). It is estimated that approximately 37.9 million people (ranging from 32.7 to 44.0 million) worldwide are living with the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), which causes acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) (World Health Organization [WHO], 2020). Significant progress has been made in HIV care with the advent of the Highly Active Antiretroviral Therapy (HAART) era. Particularly among individuals who are aware of their infection and initiate treatment early, health outcomes have improved considerably (Palella et al., 2014). In this context, the first and most critical step in accessing care services is timely HIV testing and early diagnosis (CDC, 2019). Nevertheless, according to 2017 data from developed countries, approximately 21–45% of HIV diagnoses were made at an advanced stage of infection (defined as a CD4+ cell count <350 cells/ μ L or the presence of an AIDS-defining clinical condition) (Smith et al., 2018). A global meta-analysis has demonstrated that behavioral interventions are effective in reducing sexual risk behaviors and in preventing the transmission of both HIV and other sexually transmitted infections (Kohler et al., 2019). These interventions typically deliver consistent messages that can reach broad segments of at-risk populations. Through the integration of television, radio, outdoor advertisements, and information

and communication technologies, they aim to disseminate knowledge regarding HIV transmission routes and prevention strategies (Brown et al., 2020). In this study, Google Trends data are utilized to objectively evaluate the contribution of a news story related to HIV, which gained attention on national media platforms, to public awareness. Additionally, the study aims to highlight the necessity of encouraging a more effective and proactive use of media channels in the context of raising awareness about infectious diseases (Eysenbach, 2011).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, Google Trends data -commonly used in digital epidemiological research- were utilized to assess public awareness of HIV/AIDS. Google Trends is an analytical tool that displays the frequency and regional trends of specific keyword searches over time. Using data from January 2004 to January 2025, search interest related to the keyword “HIV” was examined both globally and specifically for Turkey. The data were obtained in the form of monthly, normalized search volume indices (on a scale of 0–100) within the “web search” category. Temporal trends were analyzed, and potentially associated factors were evaluated.

RESULTS

The trends for the keyword “HIV” in Turkey were examined from 2004 to the present, across “all categories” and specifically within the “health” category.

An analysis of Google Trends data reveals two distinct peak periods in HIV-related search interest in Turkey between 2004 and the present: in 2018 and 2024 (Figure 1).

A more detailed examination shows that these increases occurred specifically in January 2018 and March 2024, respectively (Figures 2 and 4). During the surge in early 2018, a noticeable increase in search interest was observed particularly in the Southeastern Anatolia region. In contrast, the heightened interest in 2024 was especially concentrated in the province of Karabük (Figures 3 and 5). Across the entire study period, the most frequently asked question was “What is HIV?”

Figure 3

Change in the search interest for "HIV" in Turkey in 2024 by province

1	Karabük	100
2	Bayburt	97
3	Bingöl	96
4	Kars	79
5	Artvin	75

Figure 4

Change in the search interest for "HIV" in Turkey over time in 2018

Figure 5

Change in the search interest for "HIV" in Turkey in 2018 by province

1	Siirt	100
2	Kilis	77
3	Iğdır	71
4	Diyarbakır	64
5	Burdur	61

DISCUSSION

Investigating online health information-seeking behavior and utilizing monitoring tools such as Google Trends (GT) is known as infodemiology—a well-established, practical, and informative method for analyzing and predicting various disease patterns (Eysenbach, 2011). Numerous infodemiological studies have demonstrated the value of real-time data in health assessment (Preis et al., 2012). The analysis of online search queries has become a significant focus of academic research within the field of big data analytics. This study utilized Google Trends data to assess the impact of media on public awareness of HIV/AIDS at both temporal and regional levels. The findings revealed significant increases in internet search volumes during periods when media reports related to HIV were published. Notably, sharp rises in search interest were observed following events in 2018 and 2024, indicating that media content can directly influence the public's information-seeking behavior. The internet is a powerful tool for informing the public about health issues. The increase in search interest during the relevant periods was found to coincide with media coverage that captured widespread public attention. In January 2018, reports about doctors at Dicle University Hospital allegedly refusing to operate on an HIV-positive patient received widespread national media coverage, sparking public debates. Similarly, in March 2024, news about an increase in HIV cases among students at Karabük University gained significant media attention. The rise in search volume during these periods was not only notable in terms of time but also at the regional level. Changes in search behavior by province mirrored the geographic regions where the news was reported (Figures 3 and 5).

In the literature, several studies have been conducted to assess web searches related to HIV/AIDS. One study in Hong Kong, examining a 10-year period of web queries, found that news coverage had a positive impact on online search behavior concerning HIV/AIDS and men who have sex with men (Ling & Lee, 2016). Additionally, the authors observed that such search patterns tended to peak 2 to 10 weeks after the publication of related news stories. Furthermore, significant correlations have been reported between patterns of chronic diseases, including HIV, and online activity over a 10-year period (Seifter et al., 2010). In another study, Seifter and colleagues demonstrated a seasonal and geographic correlation between increased interest in Google Trends data and the incidence of Lyme disease (Seifter et al., 2010). Similarly, Bragazzi et al. (2017) found a significant correlation between public interest—measured through search queries and interactions across various web-based platforms—and Zika virus outbreaks, using big data analytics. Segev and Baram-Tsabari (2012) discussed the impact of media and education on web search behavior, concluding that media coverage—often focused on current events that raise public concern—can lead to an educational effect by motivating individuals to independently seek relevant information. Consistent with the literature, our study also demonstrated through Google Trends data that media content generating significant public attention can contribute to raising awareness about an infectious disease.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates the utility of online search data in assessing public health awareness. Significant increases in internet search interest were observed during periods when media reports related to HIV/AIDS were published, indicating that media content can influence public information-seeking behavior. The findings suggest that the interaction between media and the public may serve as a valuable tool in the context of public health. The field of infodemiology offers an innovative contribution to traditional epidemiological methods by enabling the integration of digital data sources into public health. Infodemiological analyses using tools such as Google Trends hold significant potential for the future, particularly in terms of rapid data collection, measuring public interest, and tracking sudden shifts in awareness. In this context, the broader use of online data analytics should be encouraged both for the development of public health policies and for shaping media strategies aimed at improving health literacy. Furthermore, establishing stronger collaboration between health authorities and media organizations is of critical importance to ensure the delivery of accurate and guiding health information to the public.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

- Bragazzi, N. L., Alicino, C., Trucchi, C., et al. (2017). Global response to the recent Zika virus outbreaks: Insights from big data analysis. *PLOS ONE*, *12*(9), e018526. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.018526>
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2019). Monitoring selected national HIV prevention and care objectives by using HIV surveillance data—United States and 6 dependent areas, 2017. *HIV Surveillance Supplemental Report*, *24*. <https://www.cdc.gov/hiv/pdf/library/reports/surveillance/cdc-hiv-surveillance-supplemental-report-vol-24-3.pdf>
- Eysenbach, G. (2011). Infodemiology and infoveillance: Monitoring online health information and cyber behavior for public health. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, *40*(5 Suppl. 2), S154–S158.
- Ling, R., & Lee, J. (2016). Using Google search activity for disease monitoring and health campaign evaluation in Canada: A retrospective observational study on HIV, AIDS, stroke, colorectal cancer, and marijuana use. *JMIR Public Health Surveillance*, *2*(2), e156. <https://doi.org/10.2196/publichealth.5721>
- Preis, T., Moat, H. S., Stanley, H. E., & Bishop, S. R. (2012). Quantifying the advantage of looking forward. *Scientific Reports*, *2*, 350. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep00350>
- Preis, T., Moat, H. S., & Stanley, H. E. (2013). Quantifying trading behavior in financial markets using Google Trends. *Scientific Reports*, *3*, 1684. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep01684>

Segev, E., & Baram-Tsabari, A. (2012). Online search of scientific information: Using Google data mining to better understand the roles of media and educational systems. *Public Understanding of Science*, 21(7), 813–829. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963662511432070>

Seifter, A., Schwarzwald, A., Geis, K., et al. (2010). The utility of “Google Trends” in epidemiological research: The case of Lyme disease. *Geospatial Health*, 4(2), 135–137. <https://doi.org/10.4081/gh.2010.135>

UNAIDS. (2012). *2012 UNAIDS report on the global AIDS epidemic*. https://www.unaids.org/en/resources/documents/2012/20121120_UNAIDS_Global_Report_2012

UNAIDS. (2019). *UNAIDS data 2019*. <https://www.unaids.org/en/resources/documents/2019/2019-UNAIDS-data>

UNAIDS. (2020). *UNAIDS data 2020*. <https://www.unaids.org/en/resources/documents/2020/2020-UNAIDS-data>

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Elif Negis
Izmir Kiraz No. 1 Family Health Center
Izmir, Turkey
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4070-3558>
elifnegiss@gmail.com